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Du Yanan, Yuan Min, Sun Jiangjie, Tao Fangbiao ***ABSTRACT**

Social contagion is a common way of influence in social groups, and it is one of the important research contents of group behavior. With the deep involvement of social media in people's life, users have changed from strong connection to weak connection. Exploring social contagion in social media environment is a new paradigm to understand group psychology. This paper constructs a novel social contagion model based on social media platform, analyzes the different elements of social contagion in the new environment, gives the calculation method of group emotion in social contagion, and summarizes the impact of social contagion. The purpose of this study is to use new data sources and new ways to understand social contagion and to help the governance of public emergencies.

INTRODUCTION

With the innovation of network information technology and the adjustment of mobile Internet charges, up to August 2019, nearly 99.1% of China's Internet users use mobile devices to access the network. Mobile access traffic reached 55.39 billion GB in the first half of 2019, and netizens' online time reached 27.9 hours per week[1]. The ubiquitous data production, data sharing, and data reception make the information show nuclear fission propagation. Especially, confronted with public health emergencies, individuals usually suffer from huge psychological pressure while facing health threats, because of poor predictability, wide spread and uncertain future development [2]. In the context of social media, a micro-blog, a video, a picture, a like, a repost, and other small information behaviors are subtly affecting the perception and emotions of people's lives. Asymmetry of knowledge as well as changes in individual experience and psychological pressure have caused people to be swept by spontaneous fanaticism, respond to a series of events, and publish various true or false information on social media. Through social network clicks, comments, reposts, etc., information spread across geographical boundaries and inadvertently infect others. As a process of social emotion transmission, social contagion has the characteristics of spontaneity, non-compulsion and unconsciousness. There will be interconversion between the spreaders and the infectors, and as a result, the circulating infections in the group will cause a stronger emotional outburst. Under the influence of emotions, the group will act either positively or negatively online and offline. Even more, a large-scale group event may erupt, bringing new challenges and stress to crisis management and public opinion guidance under emergencies[3, 4]. As a consequence, this article builds a social contagion model in the context of social media to understand the nature of group emotions in social infections, cognize the impact of social contagion with a rational attitude, and provide advice for crisis management and public opinion guidance under public health events.

With the help of social media platforms, users are able to enjoy ubiquitous data production, data sharing, and data reception. Compared with traditional information media, the release and reception of social media information can be carried out anytime, anywhere in quicker and easier way. Meantime, social media information spread multi-directionally. In other words, once it is released, the information will be propagated and spread in a nuclear fission style, increasing the difficulty of supervision. In addition, social media presents a form of We-Media as everyone on the platform have

the right of posting content. This implies that any social media user may become an opinion leader through information dissemination and exchange, and play an important role in the occurrence, development and diffusion of information. The social media platform has the characteristics of enhancing social communication and social influence, which makes the information highly concerned in a very short time [5]. The social media platform has formed a new social network, the connections or ties between members is weak, while groups show self-organization, randomness and complexity [6]. Affected by the environment, users can easily form conflict or consistent group behavior [7, 8].

The source of social contagion was initially used to analyze and explain group behavior [9], and it is believed that group behavior is a manifestation of group psychology and will be transformed with the change of group environment. The interaction between groups affects individual perception and behavior, which in turn leads to different irrational behaviors [10]. In the process of group behavior, participants are spontaneous, unorganized, uncontrollable and have mutual stimulation. Bulmer [11] believes that all individuals in the group form the group behavior by process participation, coordination or cooperation and circular feedback. Individual behavior will be influenced by other individuals in the group, which is the result of the interactive feedback of members in the group [12]. Controlled by individual thoughts, individual behavior also affects group behavior to some extent [13]. Among the factors that affect group behavior, psychological factors are the most important [14], and group behavior can even be predicted by group emotional intensity [15].

As one of the important focal spots of group psychology, research on group emotion is mainly carried out from two perspectives, one is to study group opinions from the perspective of simulation, and the other is to calculate group emotion level from the perspective of machine learning. With the rise of complexity research and on the basis of interdisciplinary integration, quantitative modeling and analysis based on social networks and social dynamics have achieved great success. With the help of the voter model, the majority decision model, and the continuous viewpoint evolution model established by the bounded trust model, the reasons why the group viewpoints are unified, intensified, and split under a given topic can be found. Therefore, the evolution of public opinion and its characteristics can be explained from the angle of simulation [16, 17]. In recent years, with the development of big data collection, storage, and processing technologies, machine learning methods have been widely used in social research. Based on Twitter data from August to December 2008, the literature [18] analyzed the relationship between natural gas prices, stock indexes, important political events, public emergencies, and other major events and public sentiment, for detail, the authors mainly focus on six emotions, that is anger, depression, tension, confusion, fatigue, and vigor. The literature [19] trained their prediction model on the LiveJournal data set by means of the pace regression method, to predict the emotional level of group users at a given time period. According to above research, social contagion is an important concept to explain group behavior while group emotion is an important manifestation of group infection. The environment innovation of social media platforms brings new characteristics of social infection. Therefore, it is necessary to construct a framework of social contagion under the social media platform to provide new research path of group psychology under the development of new technologies.

Social contagion modeling based on social media

Social networks have eliminated the geographical boundaries between users and built a weakly connected social ecosystem, leading traditional social infections from a strong connection infection mode to a weak connection infection mode. The proliferation and application of social media apps such as Weibo, WeChat, headlines, Kuaishou, and Douyin have enabled massive users to share information, exchange opinions, and load emotions, influencing each other from offline to online along with the social media platforms. In general, social contagion contains three key factors: the contagion promulgator, the infected person and infection information. Social contagion science believes that influence is transmitted through observation, and hints and clues of infection are scattered throughout the environment. Based on the characteristics of information behavior and user behavior of the social media platform, we build a social contagion model based on social media, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. social contagion model based on social media

The contagion promulgator and the infected person

The social media user network is a decentralized open network. In the social contagion model based on social media, participants have dual identities automatically. That is to say, individual can be a promulgator or an infector and the roles can be changed at any time. Moreover, promulgator or infector can be either individuals or groups. Since everyone on the social media platform has the right to speak, the promulgator and infector are not constrained by their identity and status, and they have equal opportunities to input and output infected information. However, the individual attributes of the participants, such as the number of fans, the number of followers, authentication tag, occupation, background endorsement, education level, Internet personality, etc., will affect the probability of infection.

The contagion information

In the social contagion model of social media, the infection information is not limited to oral and written text, because any information behavior always carries a certain amount of infection information. In detail, content such as text, emoticons, punctuation marks, pictures, videos as well as behavior such as browsing, publishing, liking, forwarding are all carriers of infected information. In terms of information content, infection information involves conflicting, typical, and vague information such as group personal safety, interests, fairness and justice, ethical beliefs, etc. More room for imagination increases the infection ability. For example, browsing shows that individuals are interested in information, comments contain ones attitude towards receiving information, and forwarding constitutes the generation process of same content. According to behavioral science, cognition, emotion, and behavior are complementary and integrated. In particular, behavior is driven by emotion, therefore, behavior is another explicit form of emotion expression, which transmits infection information.

The contagion effect

As is believed by most of the Chinese population, emotion touches people heart first. When information content and information behaviors circulate on social media, the contagion promulgator and the infected person display different emotions, attitudes, while their behaviors will be influenced. Group emotions caused by social infections do not always develop in the expected direction. With the evolution of infection information and the drift of focused topics, group emotions also evolve. Understanding the dynamic emotion distribution of group users from multiple dimensions and aspects is one of the important approaches for predicting group behavior trends and guiding the development of group behaviors. Therefore, calculating and understanding group emotions has become a direct way to estimate the effect of group infection.

Group emotion calculation of social contagion users

Group emotion representation model

It is important to clarify the definition of emotions or sentiment before calculating group emotions. The mainstream sentiment classification mainly includes the following three categories: (1) coarse-grained judgments of positive and negative tendency, which can quickly identify the voices of support and opposition within the group; (2) based on the long-standing Chinese traditional culture, the emotions are divided into six types: “happiness, anger, sadness, cheer, fear and surprise”. (3) continuous emotions in the multi-dimensional space, as each subtle social experience will be mapped to a point in the continuous space. Among above three emotion classification methods, the first two are discrete emotion modeling means, which are concise and convenient for computation, however, they cannot describe complex emotional experiences accurately. The third one is a continuous emotion modeling approach, which can represent complex emotion state more precisely, however, due to the complexity of computation, it is not common used. The scale of social media data is huge and updated in real time, making it a typical large data stream calculation task. Through balancing the computational cost and the complexity of representation, the second discrete sentiment modeling is more suitable for group sentiment computing in the social media context. Considering the historical development and evolution of Chinese language, and the extremely colloquial features of social media information, happiness and love are combined into one category, and finally five emotion states contain “affection, anger, sadness, surprise and fear” are selected in our model [20]. In addition, information will be regarded as neutral when it contains no emotion.

Computing method of infection information on social media

After preprocessing, each piece of infection information s on social media can be expressed as a collection of words, $w = \{w_1, w_2, \dots, w_{\|w\|}\}$ where $\|w\|$ represents the number of words. Matching each word in w with the words in the sentiment dictionary, we will obtain the number of words representing affection $\{w \cap p^{affection}\}$ appearing in w , the number of words representing anger $\{w \cap p^{anger}\}$, the number of words representing sadness $\{w \cap p^{sadness}\}$, the number of words representing surprise $\{w \cap p^{surprise}\}$ and the number of words representing fear $\{w \cap p^{fear}\}$. $E \in R^5$ is the emotion vector of the corpus, and then the emotion vector of information s is defined as follows:

$$E(s) = [\|w \cap p^{affection}\|, \|w \cap p^{anger}\|, \|w \cap p^{sadness}\|, \|w \cap p^{surprise}\|, \|w \cap p^{fear}\|]$$

The reason why emotion vectors rather than single dimension emotion values are used is that users who are infected often have more than one side perception when expressing their emotions. For example, the content “Parents fought against the epidemic while 8-year-old boy shed tears at home alone” not only conveys messages representing respect and affection but also involves messages of sadness such as loneliness and tears. Since the length of each piece of information is different, it is necessary to normalize the emotion vector before performing the aggregation operation. The normalization method is defined as:

$$\hat{E} = \frac{E(s)}{|E(s)|} = \frac{[\|w \cap p^{affection}\|, \|w \cap p^{anger}\|, \|w \cap p^{sadness}\|, \|w \cap p^{surprise}\|, \|w \cap p^{fear}\|]}{\sqrt{\|w \cap p^{affection}\|^2 + \|w \cap p^{anger}\|^2 + \|w \cap p^{sadness}\|^2 + \|w \cap p^{surprise}\|^2 + \|w \cap p^{fear}\|^2}}$$

The normalized emotion vector and the original vector have the same direction, and the additivity problem caused by the information length is eliminated. The sentiment of a single message is

aggregated to form the group sentiment, which is denoted as $E_g = \frac{\sum_{s \in S_T} \hat{E}(s)}{\|S_T\|}$, where $\|S_T\|$ is the volume of information.

Case study: social contagion of COVID-19

The overview of social contagion of COVID-19

The social contagion of COVID-19 is triggered by a specific public health event. The trigger is the new coronavirus pneumonia epidemic centered in Wuhan, China[21]. The epidemic was a sudden and major public health event, which was menacing [22] and quickly caused persistent social infections on social media. Information release is the basis for the spread of social infections, as exposure provides opportunities for the propagation. Using S_t to indicate the amount of information related to the new

crown epidemic at the moment t , it is believed that the greater the amount of information, the stronger the attention and the greater the infectivity. We set up a daily monitoring program on Sina Public Opinion to supervise COVID-19 related information across the network. The variation tendency of the focal information amount is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 The amount of information about COVID-19 on social media (according to Sina Public Opinion) It can be found that the intensity of attention are accompanied by the process of epidemic management. On the whole there is a nearly perfect correlation. The life cycle of concern depends on the cycle of the epidemic. From the perspective of the spatial dimension of concern, the concern originates from the incident of the new coronary pneumonia epidemic, but the focus of concern involves various subjects and events in the process of epidemic management. Concern spots are added, disappeared and evolved throughout the life cycle of social infections. Meanwhile, changes in concerns drive changes in social infections. Based on the analysis of hot topics on Weibo, a 7-dimensional focus space is obtained. The main information points involved are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. main information points on Weibo

Social contagion is formed by the attention gathered under the triggering event. The stronger the attention, the more concentrated in a certain dimension, then the stronger the ability of information to cause social infection.

The infection of group emotions can be traced and derived from the attention. he Originated from the epidemic, the social contagion of COVID-19 grasps the attention of the public in a sudden and lead to nearly uncontrolled diffusion. However, because of the different issues involved in different spaces of concern, different subjects have different positions and different self-cognitive models, making the group's emotions continue to fluctuate, as displayed in Figure 4.

Figure 4 The changes of Group emotion of COVID-19

From the perspective of the emotional distribution of social infections, positive emotions like happiness have always been present, while negative emotions such as sadness, anger, and fear dominate. Reducing the granularity of information computation, we can further obtain the details of social infection.

The typical information infection status in the social contagion of COVID-19

In the social contagion of COVID-19, the emotional and informational excitation intensity of burst information are very large, and will cause strong resonance. Figure 5 exhibits the attention degree and the group's emotional infection status of the following focal points: Shuanghuanglian, paper published by Center for Disease Control (CDC), and the fecal-oral transmission.

Figure 5. the attention degree and the group's emotional infection status of focal points within 72 hours

A blog of "Shuanghuanglian can inhibit the new coronavirus" in the mainstream media quickly infected users in groups in a short time. This blog publisher is a super promulgator with 109.98 million followers on social media. Moreover, endorsed with the official media identity, it has a strong social contagion capacity. Due to the ambiguity of information disclosure, users in the group lack the ability to distinguish, and thus they are easily infected under the epidemic situation. Driven by emotional cognition, the public are eager to take action, for example, rushing to purchase Shuanghuanglian. In the process of infection information diffusion, emotions such as panic, anger and ridicule are intertwined, and with the continuous emergence of new information and evidence, the infection capacity possessed by the infection promulgator is weakened. As a partial concern of COVID-19, the topic about Shuanghuanglian prompt individuals to play the dual roles of promulgator and the infected person, and finally immunize and eliminate the infection through new infection information and behavior.

Conclusions

Social contagion based on social media is essentially the result of striving for attention and identity. Participants under the situation of expecting attention are easily susceptible to infection information.

In this process, the more social capital the infection promulgator has, the more fans they have, the more credible the “endorsement” is, and then the easier they infect others. When the participants interpret the infection information, their emotions are often biased towards the party they think are vulnerable, especially when the infection information shows the connection with the basic needs of the public or is emotionally inclined to the vulnerable groups. When the emotional slant interpretation goes into the mind of the infected person, the group becomes extremely credulous with critical cues.

However, social infections don't merely spread bad emotions, it is necessary to consider the positive and negative effects of social infections dialectically. Positive and healthy thoughts are attached to positive social contagion emotions. Through the invisible forces of social infection, the social responsibility and personal responsibility can be transmitted to the public. It can be a useful way to touch and educate users on the social media, adjust individual's psychological state, and integrate and optimize social resources. We also found that in the emotion propagation of social infection, anger is more likely to infect users than happiness and exacerbate group anxiety. It is also more likely to cause group irrational behavior. Therefore, further investigation on the emotion of anger is essential to reveal individuals natural requirements behind this emotion. The group sadness in the social contagion will multiply, which will in turn generate anger and fear. As a powerful social infection, the emotion of fear allows person to deconstruct the perception of danger from the information they received from others. Since it is nearly impossible for everyone to immune to fear completely, this subtle and tacit diffusion exert a deterrent force to help individuals get away from injury, as a result, fear caused by social contagion is necessary. Regardless of whether the dangers actually exist, responding to these dangers and investing resources to solve the cause of fear will be helpful to avoid possible risk. As long as there is new evidence to drive away fear, social infections will be controlled naturally. Nevertheless, fear reverberates greatly in consciousness and has a great impact on group behavior, so the response to fear should be louder and more powerful to motivate the confidence of the whole group and maintain the stability of the group. Above all, it is improper to decide the goodness or badness of social infections, on the contrary, take advantage of social infections actively and effectively can make positive achievements in the management of public events.

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